

The Influence of Prolong period of ASUU Strike on Students Learning Motivation and Learning Disposition Among Undergraduate Students of Northwestern Nigeria

By

Associate Professor Kabiru Rabiou Darma

Dept of Educational Foundation

Northwest University, Kano

&

Fatima Lawan Zubairu

Dept. of Arts & Social Science Education

Northwest University, Kano

ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to investigate the influence of the ASUU strike on learning motivation and learning disposition among undergraduate students in North-western Nigeria. An explanatory mixed-method research design was used to answer the research questions. A sample of 397 students were selected from undergraduate students in North-western Nigeria using a purposive sampling procedure to provide a sample for the quantitative aspect of the study, whereas 20 students were selected using a snowball sampling procedure for the qualitative data. The instrument used for quantitative data collection was a questionnaire. It was piloted and validated, and preliminary **psychometric properties** necessitated modification and removal of items construct-irrelevant to the questionnaire. Qualitative data from interview questions that explored related issues were collected from students to support the quantitative data. Descriptive statistic using mean and standard deviation was applied to determine the level of ASUU strike, learning disposition, and learning motivation in students. It was found that the level of ASUU strike was relatively high, but learning disposition and learning motivation were low. Further analysis proved a significant influence of ASUU strike, learning motivation, and learning disposition that as stated ($r=-0.777$; $p=0.05$) for learning motivation and ($r=-0.531$; $p=0.05$) for learning disposition. The findings showed that the ASUU strike had a serious negative impact on student learning motivation and learning disposition. The qualitative data further explained that the prevalence of ASUU strike among the students and the distressing conditions experienced by students affected their learning motivation and learning disposition. It was concluded that **there is** a need for viable efforts to address some of the problems that tend to have **a negative** effect on students learning motivation and learning disposition in Nigeria. Several other suggestions and recommendations were also addressed.

Keywords: ASUU strike, Learning motivation, Learning disposition, Behavioural problems, Academic achievement

Introduction

University worldwide is regarded as the fortress as well as the of knowledge, the source of producing intellectual people, the most appropriate place set aside for transforming societal goals, yearning and aspirations and all that it want to achieve or become in future. It is also serving as a place for the incubation and for training tomorrow's leader that handle political, economic and all aspect of development of a particular nation. A university fulfills one major aspect of transforming the society to a greater level of development through providing qualitative knowledge in science, technology, art and humanities (Ike, 2001). It is a knowledge, value provider as well as future socio- economic and national development. It stands or falls in its ability or inability to deliver on this criterion. Magna Carta universitum, "The University is an independent, self-directed and organized institution at the heart of societies differently planned because of geographically, ideologically and historical heritage, it produces, scrutinizes, evaluates and promotes cultural, scientific and cultural development by research and is an initiative that serves multidisciplinary purposes of developing the nation to a greater height or level of development. This according to (Nwankwo, 2004) explains why merit has been the watchword and backbone for determining the establishment of university system – a system a student must first be fully certified academically and worthy in character before being enrolled into the system. Universities remain as the strong hold for national development, that transform the country to emerge as industrialized state capable of competing with any other country in the world of scientific innovation and technological development.

Similarly, with the roles of universities as bedrock for transforming the nation to a greater level of development and this explains why the Federal Government of Nigeria is acknowledging the university as a fulcrum and support for national development. From the 1980's and afar, the deterioration of all tiers of education was colossal and enormous. Facilities had almost collapsed and distorted, teachers and lecturers morale was at its lowest. Enabling environment for teaching and learning to take place effectively was absent. The administration of President Ibrahim Babangida desired to improve the quality of higher education formed a commission in December 1990 known as "The Gray Longe Commission" to address the problems facing higher education in Nigeria including that of universities operating in the country. The Federal Government authorized the commission to scrutinize and review the post-independence Nigerian Higher Education after Lord Ashby's Commission of 1959 that characterized with lot of obstacles hindering the development of the country to a greater height. The commission was given terms of reference amongst which were:

1. To re-examine the developmental roles of universities in developmental roles of universities in developing countries such as Nigeria.
2. To Determine the middle and higher-level manpower supply and demand of the country and advice in under/over population and under/over utilization of the same.
3. To scrutinize the availability and adequacy of academic staff in universities.

4. Investigates the nature, sources and criteria of funding in higher education institutions. (Especially universities) with a view to improving the situation and guaranteeing steady source of funds for optimal functional of these institutions.
5. Review the general condition of staff in higher educational institutions such as salaries, pensions and retirement benefit, housing of the public service and private sector and particularly to stemming the brain phenomenon.
6. Review the criteria for appointment of administration, including the Vice Chancellors, Provosts, Rectors, Registrars, and other Principal Officers, their term of office and the process of renewal of their appointment.
7. To ensure quality assurance governance in academic activities Administration activities, policy and decision making among principal officers, other staff and students of the Institution.
8. Good governance by ensuring quality input, process and Productivity.
9. Variability in the quality assurance governance and management frame work are maintained.
10. Managing of fund through accountability, prudence, and transparency is maintained.
11. Through external and Internal Variables or Parameters such as monitoring and Inspection, governance assessment visit, External auditing of financial transaction and Objective assessment by stakeholders.
12. To ensure that vice chancellors and Principal Officers of all Universities do not stray from the Vision, Mission and objectives of their respective Universities.

The commission organized special session, workshop and conferences with the professionals comprising of eminent personalities and educationist across the country, from whose knowledge and experience of the educational system in Nigeria it benefited immensely. Finally, the commission well-defined higher education as the kind of education in higher educational institution especially in universities, which produce high level and middle level manpower, but not specialized set up by professional bodies. The commission noted that the goals and objectives among others include: teaching research and public service, also the commission observed that Nigerian universities had established standard comparable to the best in other parts of the world. The commission, however, frowned at the discovery that the following physical conditions are still the trademarks of the Nigerian universities and these include;

- i. Dilapidated workshops equipment in most of the higher institutions.
- ii. Shortages of facilities affecting the universities in Nigeria such as libraries, lecture rooms, laboratories and work farms. The commission was also shocked by the fact that universities have not achieved and deviated seriously from the set of the goals and objectives for which they were set up, owing to incessant disruption in the academic flow chart caused by strike actions, industrial unrest, students' hooliganism, political instability, etc.

This study will take an interest in investigating critically the prolong period of Academic Staff Union of the University (ASUU) strike in 2022 that last for eight consecutive month and its effect on students' learning motivation and learning disposition among university students of North-western Nigeria. However, the incessant strikes carried out by ASUU membership tend to have unfavourable impact on students learning and development to the greater level. Meanwhile, all this industrial action has disrupted the academics activities of the university for years while the quality of education ditched to students is half-baked. The academic performance of students is getting poorer every section due to incessant industrial action of the Academic Staff Union of the university (ASUU). Kazeem and Ige (2010) reported that disruption of academic activities resulting from industrial action of the ASUU has crippled the Nigerian educational system as the product of the Nigerian tertiary institution are half baked due to disrupted academic calendar.

Objectives of the study

This study is targeted to achieve the following objectives

- I. To determine the level of ASUU strike, learning motivation and learning motivation among undergraduate students in North-western Nigeria.
- II. To determine the influence of ASUU strike on students learning motivation and learning disposition among undergraduate students in Northwestern Nigeria.

Research Questions

This research seeks to find answer to the following research questions:

- I. What are the levels of ASUU strike on learning motivation and learning disposition among the undergraduate students in North-western Nigeria?
- II. Are there any significant influences of ASUU strike on students learning motivation and learning disposition among undergraduate students in North-western Nigeria?

Statement of the Problem

The incessant strikes action by the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) has inadvertently and negatively affected the quality of teaching and learning among the undergraduate students of universities in Nigeria; it typically poses a lot of obstacles and challenges to their study habit, duration, performance in examinations and their final grading that determine class of degree obtained by undergraduate students. The students are forced to stay away from school and remain at home for a long time; most of them are completely cut off from academic activities and other curricular activities that support learning as conditions at home may not favour learning to take place effectively and efficiently. In such a situation of prevailing of unconducive atmosphere for learning students become frustrated because of long expectation of school resumption that is far from been known and determine. With this development some of the students while at home staying redundant can easily engaged in some anti-social behavior that may affect their learning and development. In some cases they are easy joins for criminal activities, such as armed robbery, kidnapping, and rape. This has made them a problem to the

society peace and order in Nigeria. However the extent to which ASUU strikes affects students' learning motivation and learning disposition require a close and critical examination and this may provide a dependable solution to some of the major problems associated with ASUU strike on students learning and development.

Scope and Limitations

The research on the influence of ASUU strikes on students' academic learning motivation and learning disposition in Northwestern Nigeria' is a comprehensive study. It employs a geographical and chronological emphasis to study the consequences of these strikes on students learning motivation and learning disposition across a specified time (2022) specifically, from February 2022 towards the end of the year. The study involves only undergraduate students from different faculties both males and females that witnessed the prolong period of ASUU strike of 2022. The impact evaluation encompasses the entire dimension for learning motivation such as competence, autonomy/control, interest/value, and relatedness and as for learning disposition it's comprised of some variables depicting attitude, habit of mind and behaviours that influence students approach to learning. The research takes a mixed-methods approach in a form of explanatory, integrating quantitative and qualitative data to provide the divergent views and opinions on how the ASUU strike influence students learning motivation and disposition among the undergraduate students of Northwestern Nigeria. The report also presents policy recommendations for stakeholders to limit the negative consequences of strikes and protect the quality of education. However, the study admits its limitations, highlighting the need for wider investigations covering diverse geographies and durations.

Literature Review

The Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) was created in 1978 to improve the welfare and interests of its members and solve some of the major problems and challenges affecting university education system in Nigeria. The union launched its industrial action in 1980 to protest against the dismissal of six lecturers from the University of Lagos, as legalized by Justice Belonwu Visitation Panel Report. The union continues to put more pressure of financing universities, addressing of brain drain, poor salary structure, and improved university systems. The Elongated University Salary Structure (EUSS) was one of a prominent point of disagreement in 1988 between ASUU and federal government owing to the lack of implementation. In 1984, ASUU went on to another strike to resist deregulation of the economy and military rule. In 1986, ASUU strongly criticized and condemned the adoption and implementation of Structural Adjustment Programmes (SAP) by Ibrahim Babangida's administration and the merciless killing of students at Ahmadu Bello University Zaria by mobile Police. In 1987, ASUU sought the implementation of the Elongated University Salary Scale and a joint bargaining committee between ASUU and the federal government to address problems existing in universities. In 1993, ASUU was banned again by federal government resulting from disobeying the Industrial Arbitration Panel's decision to stop industrial action.

With these prevailing developments as highlighted in the earlier, in 2001, ASUU embarked on strike action on problems associated to finance of universities and low wage received by lecturers, retirement age, and non-implementation of various agreements between ASUU and federal government. The ASUU, a banned organization in Nigeria, was resurrected by General Abdulsalami in 1999 to restore military pride and boost the pay of academic workers. However, the new administration of Abdus-salami Abubakar incorporated a neo-liberal position, considering education as a private duty. In 2000, the federal government promised to spend at least 26% of yearly budgets for education, with half of this going to higher education to improve the quality of university education system and other institution of higher learning in the state. However, decision fell down, resulting for ASUU take another strike in 2001 as the only alternative, in June 2009, ASUU instructed its members at federal and state universities nationwide to gone for an indefinite strike following disagreement with the Federal Governments over a treaty signed two and a half years before. After three months of strikes, ASUU and other staff unions reached an agreement through memorandum of understanding signed between two parties to stop the strike.

Similarly, salary structure of university lecturers in Nigeria played a crucial in bringing disagreement between ASUU memberships and the Federal government. The long-term fall in salary and conditions of service among Nigerian academics traced back its historical genesis to the immediate post-independence era. At independence, university personnel received well-paid salary and occupied a comparatively high position compared to their counterparts working in other departments in the state civil service. However, with the coming of the military rule into Nigerian politics in 1966, there was a steady transformation in the relative payment of wages and salaries among various occupational groups throughout the country, leading to a rising imbalance and inequality among working classes in Nigeria. By 1966, the annual pay of a university professor remained £3,000. This sum was nevertheless more than a Federal Minister's pay of £2,700 and a senior civil worker of the level of Permanent Secretary who was paid between £2,500 and £2,940. French perks such as housing, allowances, social prestige, and working conditions were appealing to academics, making them the envy of public officials.

The National Association of University Teachers (NAUT) in Nigeria was formerly the most passive workers' organization, focused on providing superior education. However, in the 1970s, severe inflation led to a walkout to negotiate salary hikes, which was met with hostility by the military leadership. This led to the founding of ASUU in 1978.

The desire of federal government to harmonize and make some changes in civil service under the "unified public service" suggestion of 1975 severely underestimated as well as underrated university lecturers in Nigeria institutions of higher learning. Under this plan, university professors' wages were restricted at £11,568, making them equal with state-level Permanent Secretary but lower than serving in federal level. This led to a class dominant project of the Nigerian military class in society that opened for the prevalence of inequality and class structure among the citizenry. Incessant strike activities engaged by ASUU stated initially as a battle for class survival. One of the union's requests was the reinstatement of the 20% disparity in the

University Salary Structure (USS), which had been reduced by the Structural Adjustment Program (SAP) of the Ibrahim Babangida regime. However, the government introduced the Elongated University Salary Structure (EUSS) under the SAP, making private sector wages more appealing than public sector pay.

ASUU has tried to engage the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) since 1992 in talks including collective bargaining on wage and welfare packages for academic workers. Between 1993, 2008 and 2022, Nigerian colleges were closed for over 36 months owing to different strike activities. Disputes concerning salary structure for academics remain a major part, but they are implicitly related to the deterioration in the economic position of Nigerian academics over the years. The rise to dominance of the Nigerian military and structural adjustment processes have pushed constraints on public sector expenditure, leading to an increasingly political struggle.

METHODOLOGY

i. Research Design

The Northwest remains a populous and the one of the most important region among six geopolitical zones constituting Nigeria. It comprises six states – Kano, Kaduna, Katsina Sokoto, Zamfara, and Kebbi State respectively. This study employed an **Explanatory Mixed-method Research** Design. This design comprises of two different phases: starting first with quantitative data and then followed by qualitative data (Creswell et al. 2003). In this design, a researcher begins by collecting and analysing the quantitative data (numeric) data then follow by qualitative data with the hope of supporting and giving additional meaning to the quantitative findings. The qualitative data (text) collected by the researcher and analysed second in the sequence helps to clearly describe or elaborate in another dimension the results obtained in the quantitative phase that deals with the numerical data. The qualitative phase that deals with text is purely built on the first, quantitative phase, and the two are connected and complementary with one another in the intermediate study for better exploration of the problem under investigation.

The reason for adopting this approach or method is that the quantitative data and their subsequent analysis provide a general overview and understanding of the research problem under investigation. The qualitative data and their subsequent analysis enhance and explain more clearly those statistical results by exploring participants' views and opinions more profoundly and intensely (Rossman, & Wilson, 1985; Tashakkori, & Teddlie, 1988; Ivankova, Creswell, & Stick, 2009)

The Researcher distribute questionnaire titled Questionnaire for Exploring the Influence of ASUU Strike on Student Learning Motivation and Learning Disposition among Undergraduate Students in North-western Nigeria. The researcher distributed the questionnaire to the students with the help of research assistant and then after responding to the items of the questionnaire and engaged in face to face interview with the students in order to collect divergent information from the students depicting the influence of ASUU strike on their learning motivation and disposition as a result of the prevalence of ASUU strike in 2022.

Population of the Study

The population of this study were includes undergraduate students 2020/2021 and 2023/2024 academic session across the universities both male and female students that experienced the prolong period of ASUU in 2022, which is three thousand, five hundred and ninety six (3596) students, comprising of present 300 levels and present 400 levels students, they were choose because of their experience on ASUU strike during the course of studies, and their perspective were exploited in the course of this research.

iii. Sample and Sampling

Multistage sampling methods were adopted in this study. it refers to sampling plans where the sampling is carried out in stages using smaller and smaller sampling units at each stage Cost and speed that the survey can be done in, Convenience of finding the survey sample, Normally more accurate than cluster sampling for the same size sample but it disadvantage are not as accurate as Simple Random Sample if the sample is the same size, More testing is difficult to do. North east has (6) states as time of this research work from where six (12) universities was selected by systematic random sampling. Therefore, a Total number of six (12) universities was selected.

iv. Instrument of Data Collection

The research instrument was questionnaires and Interview. A comprehensive questionnaire was designed and administered to the respondents, the questionnaire will contained closed and open ended questions, each of the respondents was asked to check for an option that best suits the question (s) and fill in their responses as appropriate on the questionnaire spaces provided. The questions were divided into four sections A, B and C, the first section contained ASUU strike Questionnaire, the second part compose of learning motivation questionnaire while the third section contain learning disposition and the last segment comprises of students information. The questionnaire aim to explore students' views and opinions with regard to the influence of ASUU strike on their learning motivation and learning disposition

v. Content Validity

An instrument is said to be valid if it essentially measures what it is intended to measure. The content validity of the PD-LADIS was first assessed by two (2) experts at the school of education Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, thereafter, the research submitted to selected experts in the field of Psychology, higher education/language art education and measurement and evaluation at the Bayero University, Kano in Nigeria. The detailed information of the content experts is presented in Table 1.1. below:

SN	Expert	Qualification	Academic Rank	Field of Study
1	Expert A	PhD	Professor	Education Psychology
2	Expert B	PhD	Professor	Higher

				Education/Language
3	Expert C	PhD	Senior Lecturer	Educational Psychology
4	Expert D	PhD	Senior Lecturer	Measurement & Evaluation

The experts validated the instruments in terms of clarity of language, the ambiguity of the statements, relevance to the topic and appropriateness of the items. After scrutinising the instruments, some constructive suggestions and corrections were made by the experts before producing the final draft of the instruments for pilot testing. Additionally, the ratings provided by these experts were used to compute the inter-rater reliability using Kappa statistics (see Table 1.2). The questionnaires have adequate content validity with the modified Kappa of 0.90 for all the two sub-scales Polit, Beck, & Owen, 2007).

Table2.1 Kappa Statistics

SN	Sub-scale	Kappa
1	Learning Motivation	0.92
2	Learning Disposition	0.85
Total		0.90

vi. Reliability (Internal Consistency)

The Rasch Measurement approach was used to estimate the reliability of the PD-LADIS. The reliability coefficient of the scales in items based on relevant standards has excellent items as well as adequate internal consistency reliability (Aziz, Zaharim, Fuad, Nopiah, 2013). The summary presented in Table 3.8 showed that the person sample used in the Test is large enough to confirm the item difficulty hierarchy of the test items.

Table 3.1 Summary Statistics

SN	Reliability	ASUU strike	Learning Disposition
1	Item Reliability	0.97	0.94
2	Item Separation	6.04	3.87
3	Cronbach Alpha	0.86	0.84

The reliability coefficients presented in Table 3.8 revealed the item reliabilities of 0.97, and 0.94, with corresponding Cronbach Alpha of 0.86 and 0.84 for ASUU strike and Learning Disposition respectively. The reliability of these parameters was considered satisfactory because according to Cohen, Morrison, & Callaway, (2013) a Cronbach’s alpha scale greater than 0.70 is acceptable for the internal consistency reliability of the items and can therefore be accepted for research purpose.

vii. Administration of Questionnaire

Qualitative and quantitative methodologies were adopted for data generation. Hence questionnaires and interviews were employed to obtain data from the respondents. The questionnaires were administered to the respondents (Students) in the selected universities of the chosen state. Three hundred and ninety seven (397) questionnaires were administered and in-depth interviews were conducted with some randomly selected students from the research sample.

viii. Method of Data Analysis

The data gathered was analyzed through the use of standard deviation and mean score to determine the level of ASUU strike, learning motivation and learning disposition among undergraduate students. More so, the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) using Chi-Square as a statistical tool to interpret the quantitative data collected with the questionnaire, and content analysis was adopted in interpreting the qualitative data for the purpose of providing additional support to the quantitative findings.

RESULTS

4.1 Level of ASUU strike among undergraduate students

SN	Item	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	The strike caused disaster to my university education	397	3.63	1.090
2	School activities disrupted and failed	397	3.65	1.118
3	My learning activities at home disrupted	397	3.13	1.192
4	Divert students’ attention from the university.	397	3.71	1.039
5	Attentions from my lecturers are no longer available.	397	3.36	1.082
6	Relation with my course mate reduce	397	3.71	.953
7	Library visitation for research reduced drastically.	397	3.24	1.118
8	Classroom activities are not interesting any more	397	3.56	1.114
9	Improvement in teaching and learning activities at university	397	1.52	.525
10	Negative relation with some of our lecturers	397	3.70	.876
11	Improvements in instructional facilities at university	397	1.90	.851
12	Improvements in library services at university.	397	1.76	.751

SN	Item	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
13	Mass destruction of laboratory facilities.	397	3.47	.975
14	Promote school maintenance	397	3.64	1.156
15	Difficult to manage and supervise university education	397	3.42	1.266
16	Cause difficulty in attending university regularly	397	3.24	1.208
17	Force female students for marry	397	3.41	1.103
18	Force many students to abscond university	397	3.19	1.174
19	Promote rapid community participation on university education.	397	1.60	.750
20	Delay for students' graduation.	397	3.61	1.045
21	Make university education boring.	397	3.58	1.162
22	Reduce students desire to proceed to postgraduate study	397	3.10	1.213
23	Reduce students desire to participate in extracurricular activities outside the university	397	3.39	1.085
24	Disruption of academic calendar	397	3.77	1.090
25	Make university education unsafe	397	4.02	.941
26	Show the weakness of federal government in handling university education.	397	3.71	1.045
27	Cause mistrust and suspicion between university lectures and community members.	397	3.68	1.131
28	Cause serious mistrust between lecturers and government	397	3.05	1.383
29	Lecturers failure to attend university regularly	397	3.48	1.218
30	Delay towards completion of my university in time	397	4.06	.969
Overall Mean		397	3.27	0.231

The results presented in Table 4. 3 above show that the undergraduate students in North-western Nigeria who participated in this study scored above 3.00 in all the ASUU strike assessment items except in 3 items (9, 11, and 12). However, overall, the respondents scored a mean of 3.50 (SD=0.211) which is higher than the overall average of 3.00. These results depicted that the level of ASUU strike among undergraduate students in North-western Nigeria relatively *high*.

Table 4.2 Level of Learning Disposition

To determine the level of learning disposition among undergraduate students in North-western Nigeria. The responses from the respondents on the learning disposition scale were used to conduct a descriptive statistical analysis using mean and standard deviation. The results are presented in Table 4.4 based on the students' scores on Learning Disposition.

Table **Error! No text of specified style in document.** 2.1 Level of Learning Disposition

SN	Item	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	I am a weak person	397	1.68	.972
2	I like to do challenging tasks	397	1.90	1.017
3	I set for myself high scores which I believe I can achieve	397	2.29	1.046
4	I find it difficult to express myself clearly in class when I am facing challenges	397	2.52	1.160
5	I can learn most things in our class if I try	397	1.94	.929
6	I concentrate fully when I'm trying to master new things	397	3.74	1.054
7	My brain comes up with lots of creative ideas	397	3.08	1.287
8	I like making links between what I learn at school in my head	397	1.92	.878
9	I make good use of things around me to help me learn	397	2.28	1.035
10	I'm honest and satisfied with myself about how well I'm doing in school.	397	2.52	1.177
11	I'm well aware of how I learn best in school	397	2.58	1.134
12	I enjoy learning new things with other people	397	2.38	1.130
13	I'm ready to accept feedback and advice from classmates	397	1.92	.930
14	I help others see how they could improve	397	2.25	1.019
15	I don't want to speak my opinion in a large group	397	2.26	.997
16	I tend to make decisions in class easily and quickly	397	2.05	.969
17	I am good at expressing my emotions in school	397	2.13	.907
18	I am prepared to take shortcuts when solving a problem in school	397	2.03	.991
19	I like to ask questions on something that I don't know clearly in a class	397	1.88	.788
20	I often speak my mind in class regardless of the consequences	397	2.05	.916
21	I tend to be flexible with rules and regulations in the school	397	2.27	1.008
22	I can enjoy myself at any time in the class	397	2.23	1.090
23	I do not like to try new things	397	3.42	.999
24	I find it difficult to share personal information in school	397	3.28	.985
25	I am afraid to act silly around my classmates	397	2.22	1.092
	Overall Mean	397	2.45	0.179

The results presented in Table 4.4 above show that the undergraduate students in North-western Nigeria who participated in this study scored less than 3.00 in all the learning disposition assessment items except in 4 items (6,7, 23, and 24). However, overall, the respondents scored a mean of 2.45 (SD=0.179) which is lower than the overall average of 3.00. These results depicted that the level of learning disposition among undergraduate students in North-western Nigeria relatively **low**. This is further summarized in Table 4.6.

1.1.1 Level of Learning Motivation

To determine the level of learning motivation among undergraduate students in North-western Nigeria. The responses from the respondents on learning motivation were used to conduct a descriptive statistical analysis using mean and standard deviation. The results are presented in Table 4.3 based on the students' scores on Learning Motivation.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document..3 Level of Learning Motivation

SNItem	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
1 I prefer lessons that encourage me to learn new things in our school.	397	2.24	1.073
2 I prefer lessons that arouse my interest even if it is difficult to learn in our school	397	2.13	.993
3 The most important thing for me in the school is to understand the topics taught to us by our teachers.	397	2.39	1.117
4 When I have the opportunity in school, I chose lessons that I can learn from even if they don't guarantee a good grade.	397	2.37	1.045
5 The most important thing for me in the school is improving my performance in order to obtain good grades.	397	2.11	.929
6 Getting a good grade in the class is the most satisfying thing for me right now.	397	2.49	1.058
7 If I can, I want to get better grades in our class than most of the other students.	397	2.27	1.029
8 I want to do well in our class because it is important to show my ability to my family and friends	397	2.03	.907
9 I think I will be able to use what I learn from our teachers in other courses.	397	2.22	1.082
10 It is important for me to learn the subjects offered in our school.	397	2.30	1.131
11 I am very interested in the subjects offered in our school.	397	2.23	1.146
12 I think the subjects offered in our school is useful for me to learn	397	1.96	.858
13 I like all the subjects taught in our school	397	2.88	1.178

SN Item	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
14 Understanding all the subjects taught in our school is very important to me.	397	3.28	1.117
15 If I study hard, then it is easy for me to learn better in the class.	397	3.10	1.129
16 It is my own fault that I don't work hard to learn other subjects offered in our school.	397	2.55	1.148
17 If I work hard, then I will understand clearly all the subjects taught in our school.	397	2.13	.994
18 If I don't understand the lesson taught in the class, it is because I didn't try hard enough	397	2.62	1.169
19 I believe I will achieve success in our class.	397	2.41	1.159
20 I'm sure I can understand the difficult topic taught by our teachers.	397	2.36	1.067
21 I'm confident I can learn the basic concepts taught in our class.	397	2.29	1.085
22 I'm confident I can understand the most difficult topic presented by our teachers in the class.	397	3.02	1.179
23 I'm confident I can perform better on assignments and tests given by our teachers	397	3.14	1.067
24 I expect to perform academically better in our school.	397	3.14	1.140
25 I'm sure I can master the skills being taught in our class.	396	3.09	1.145
Overall Mean	397	2.51	0.214

The results presented in Table 4.3 show that the undergraduate students in North-western Nigeria who participated in this study scored less than 3.00 in all the learning motivation assessment items except in 6 items (14, 15, 22, 23, 24, and 25). However, overall, the respondents scored a mean of 2.51 (SD=0.214) which is lower than the overall average of 3.00. These results depicted that the level of learning motivation among undergraduate students in North-western Nigeria relatively **low**. This is further summarized in Table 4.3.

Table 4.7 below provides an overall summary of the students’ scores in the level of ASUU strike, learning motivation and learning motivation among undergraduate students in North-western in Northern Nigeria.

Influence of Asuu Strike on Learning Motivation

ASUU strike	Learning Motivation	Results
		- 0.777(000)

Based on the result presented in Figure 4.9, using Structural Equation Model (SEM) it can be deduced that there is a negative ($r = -0.777$) but significant ($p = 0.00$) influence of ASUU strike on learning motivation among undergraduate students in North-western Nigeria. This means that strike carried out by ASUU membership in 2022 negatively and significantly affects students learning Motivation. Thus, on the basis of this finding, it can be inferred that there is a significant as well as negative relationship between ASUU strike and learning motivation among undergraduate students in North-western Nigeria.

Influence of ASUU on Leaning Disposition

ASUU strike	Learning Disposition	Results
		- 0.5.31(000)

From the result above structural analysis carried out using SmartPLS presented in Figure 4.11, it can be presumed that there is a negative ($r = -0.531$) but significant ($p = 0.00$) influence between ASUU Strike and learning disposition among the undergraduate students in North-western Nigeria. This means that the 2022 strike negatively and significantly affects students learning disposition. Thus, based on this finding, it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between ASUU Strike and learning disposition among undergraduate students.

Discussing of Findings

The purpose of university education is to help produce competent work force that will help contribute to the growth and development of the Nigerian society in all spheres of life: educationally, economically, socially, religiously, politically and otherwise. This laudable goal of Nigerian universities cannot be, and have not been perfectly attained in the event of unstable university educational system as a result of government insensitivity to the required need of university education. To curb this negligence, staff of Nigerian universities especially ASUU as a body union for all academic staff resort mostly, to the use of the non-violent instrument of civil disobedience (strike action) to drive home their demands which in-turn brought about some changes and challenges in the academic system.

The strike carried out by ASUU membership in 2022 seeking to address some of the major problems and challenges surrounding the entire university education system in Nigeria greatly affected the students learning motivation and learning disposition. The levels of the strike as observed from results indicated in table 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3 was high by scoring the overall mean scores of 3.27, 2.5 and 2.88 for ASUU strike, learning motivation and learning disposition respectively. This is clear indication that the strike tends to have strong influence on students learning and development thereby causing uncertainty and backwardness in the entire university education system in Nigeria.

Not just in Nigeria but across the globe, every student has a desire to complete his/her university course in time and within a stipulated period without any form of glitch or problem either to academic performance or to the number of years specified. The result obtained in **table 4.4** indicate that ASUU strike has negatively affect student learning motivation and learning disposition among undergraduate students in north-western part of Nigeria by promoting poor reading habit . It is well known that poor reading habit developed by many undergraduate students can significantly hinder learning motivation by creating a cycle of frustration and disengagement. Students who struggle with reading may experience difficulty understanding course material, leading to lower academic performance and decreased self-esteem. This, in turn, can diminish their interest in learning and their desire to put in the effort required to succeed. This is in line with the findings of Olusegun (2013) and Nwagbala, et, al (2023) whose finding indicate that a little above average of the student agreed that ASUU strike negatively affect their learning motivation by drastically and negatively affecting academic performance, reading habit, examination being tough after strike call off and CGPA reduces when examinations are conducted immediately after ASUU strike. This is also confirmed by Nwanyanwu, et, al., (2023) who opined that ASSU strikes reduce students' reading abilities and learning motivation as learning is put on- hold for a long period. The acquired knowledge during the session is forgotten. This encourages a read-and-pass attitude among the students, thereby metamorphosing into students who go after the certificate rather than the knowledge. Also based on the findings of the study, ASUU strike does make student lose confidence on academic being their career which is also in line with the findings of Angelina. (2021) Ardo &Ardo;Nwagbala, et., al (2023) and channels television interview of the chairman of ASSU (2013) who emphasize that ASUU are making students lose confidence in academics as significance to their career. These developments metamorphose to affect students learning motivation.

Based from the finding of the study ASUU strikes in Nigeria have a significant negative impact on students' learning disposition leading to increased anxiety and stress. Prolonged strikes can also foster a sense of hopelessness and despair, further hindering engagement with studies that negatively impacted students learning disposition. A poor learning disposition is characterized by negative attitudes and behaviors that hinder a student's ability to engage with and benefit from learning experiences. This includes unwillingness to try new things, difficulty persisting with challenges, and negative self-perception related to learning. It is well known facts that the findings revealed student with poor learning disposition does not read his books, does

not attend class regularly, does not listen attentively to the lectures shows or displays negative traits of fighting other in class room, creating unfriendly atmosphere such that other students avoid moving or associating with him/her and exhibit other negative and antisocial disposition. An antisocial disposition refers to a tendency to avoid social interaction and display a lack of concern for the well-being of others. It can manifest as a personality trait or, in more severe cases, be a symptom of antisocial personality disorder (ASPD). However, findings of this negative effect of ASUU strike on learning disposition conform with the research works of Osuorji and David, 2014; Michael Baker, 2013; Gabbrielle Wills, 2014 Olaniyi and Aina, 2014, Ayeni and Kolawole, 2014; Olupaimo, 2014; Olusegun Ajayi, 2013 Asua, Akwonya,. & Adzua, (2019).. Findings from these scholars revealed the emergence of behavioural problems that cannot commensurate with learning among the undergraduate students of Nigerian universities thus greatly affecting learning disposition.

Similarly, base from the findings of the study there exist a significant effect of ASUU strike on students learning motivation and learning disposition base on gender differences that existed among undergraduate students of Northwestern part of Nigeria, and with this development we can conclude that the strike tend to have significant impact on male students learning motivation and learning disposition compare to their female counterpart To be precise, ASUU strikes in Nigeria have a notable negative impact on male student behavior, leading to increased idleness, anxiety, depression, and even involvement in social vices like drug abuse and criminal activities. In view of this, findings from the study also found out that there is significant difference in the mean response of science undergraduate students and the rest of faculties on the impact of academic staff union of universities strike action on learning motivation and learning disposition among undergraduate students in North-western Nigeria. In line with finding of this study .

References

- Adesulu, D. (2012). Incessant ASUU strikes: bane of education sector. *Vanguard. Lagos, Nigeria: Vanguard Media.*
- Agbo, C. E., Chima, U. E., Omotayo, F. O., Ngige, P. A., Amoke, J. C., Mbaji, M. S., ... & Isah, A. (2024). A Cross-sectional Study on Effects of University Closure Due to Industrial Disputes on Pharmacy Students. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 88(9), 101253.
- Akintoye, E. O., & Uhunmwangho, S. O. (2018). Analysis of the effects of frequent strikes on academic performance of students in universities in Nigeria: Edo State as a focal point. *African Research Review*, 12(1), 56-65.
- Angelina C. N. (2021). The Causes And Effects Of Asuu Strike On Academic Activities Of Public University

Students In Nigeria. African Journal of Social and Behavioural Sciences (AJSBS) Volume 12, Number 1(2022) ISSN: 2141-209XA.

Ardo, G., Ardo, T., & Ubandawaki, U. (2020). Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) industrial action impact on student's academic performance in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, 2013/2014 academic session. *International Scholar Journal of Arts and Social Science Research*, 3(4), 172-181.

Asua, K. D., Akwonya, A. C. & Adzua, N. D. (2019). Effect of strike action on the academic performance of vocational and technical studies in Makurdi. *Education Review Letters*, 4 (12), 1-8

Ayeni, O. G. and Kolawole, O. (2014) The Incessant Conflicts and Strikes and their Effect on the Achievement of Goals of Business Education In Tertiary Institution in Ekiti State. Association of Business Educators of Nigeria. Compiled Journal Articles

Creswell, J. W., Plano Clark, V. L., Gutmann, M. L., & Hanson, W. E. (2003). Advanced mixed methods research designs. *Handbook of mixed methods in social and behavioral research*, 209(240), 209-240. Kazeem, K., & Ige, O. (2010). Redressing the growing concern of the education sector in Nigeria. *Edo journal of counselling*, 3(1), 40-49.

Ivankova, N. V., & Creswell, J. W. (2009). Mixed methods. *Qualitative research in applied linguistics: A practical introduction*, 23, 135-161.

Michael, B. (2013) Industrial Action in Schools: Strikes and Student Achievement. Canada Labour Market and Skill Researcher Network. CLSRN Working Paper No. 111

Nwagbala Stella Chinelo, PhD¹, Okafor Joy Ndidiamaka², Ani Anthony Ejike³ (2023) ASUU Strike on the Academic Performance of Students in Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria, *European Journal of Science, innovation and Technology* 3(3) 274 – 287.

Nwanko, O. (2004). Gender Inequality and Reproductive Rights: A Case for Coordinated Judicial Approach: Proceedings of a Judicial Colloquium on Reproductive Health and Rights.

Olaniyi, O. N. and Aina, M. A. (2014) Incessant Strikes and its Effects on Business Education Programme. Association of Business Educators of Nigeria. Compiled Journal Articles.

Olupayimo, E. O. (2014) An Examination of the Impact of Incessant Strikes on Skills Acquisition in Business Education. Association of Business Educators of Nigeria. Compiled Journal Articles.

Olusegun J. A. (2013) ASUU Strikes and Academic Performance of Students in Ekiti State University Ado-Ekiti, *international Journal of Manag Bus. Res* 4(1) Pp 19 – 34.

Osuorji, A. N., & David, S. (2014). The effect of incessant strikes on academic performance of Business Education students in ABU, Zaria. *Association of Business Educators of Nigeria*.

Rossmann, G. B., & Wilson, B. L. (1985). Numbers and words: Combining quantitative and qualitative methods in a single large-scale evaluation study. *Evaluation review*, 9(5), 627-643.

Teddlie, C., & Tashakkori, A. (2011). Mixed methods research. *The Sage handbook of qualitative research*, 4(1), 285-300.